

Observation on the arid rain spider *Parapalystes lycosinus* (Pocock, 1900) in South Africa (Arachnida: Araneae)

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ABSTRACT: The arid rain spider *Parapalystes lycosinus* (Pocock, 1900) is an endemic South African species. It was originally described from Port Elizabeth in the Eastern Cape 125 years ago. Since then, very little has been discussed. The general morphology of the species based on photographs of live specimens is discussed. Notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa, and conservation status and threats are provided.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Parapalystes* erected by Croeser (1996) is represented by five species endemics to South Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2025). Croeser revised *Palystes* in 1996 and erected the genus *Parapalystes*, with *Parapalystes euphorbiae* from the north-western Cape as the type species. He transferred four *Palystes* species to *Parapalystes*: *P. cultrifer* (Pocock, 1900), described from Grahamstown; *P. lycosinus* Pocock, 1900, from Port Elizabeth; *Ocypete megacephala* C.L. Koch, 1845, from Cape of Good Hope; and *P. whiteae* Pocock, 1902, also from Grahamstown.

Members of *Parapalystes* resemble *Palystes* with respect to eye arrangement and general body shape and posture, and they usually have a white band on the clypeal edge. However, they differ from *Palystes* in the following aspects: the cephalic region of the carapace is domed posterior to the posterior eye row and is dorsally decorated by two fine white lines, which are thinly divided, from the middle posterior eye row to the white patch immediately anterior to the fovea. The sternum is black except for a white to yellow pattern on the anterior third in some species. The abdomen has a distinct heart mark, and the leg coxae have two to five round black marks ventrally, and there are distinct genital differences between the species (Croeser, 1996).

In this paper, we revisit the arid rain spider *Parapalystes lycosinus* that was described by Pocock 125 years ago. Very little is known about the species, and in the first spider atlas (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010), the species was known only from one additional locality, the Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 1999). During the South African National Surveys of Arachnida (SANSA) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2015), the species was also sampled from the Addo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020) and six other localities in both the Eastern and Western Cape provinces, as listed in the Sparassidae Photo Identification guide (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022). In this paper, we make all information on *P. lycosinus* available. Unfortunately, the original description of the species lacks detail. Nothing has been added except for the images of the genitalia provided by Jäger & Kunz (2005).

METHODS

Specimens collected during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) surveys were deposited as voucher specimens in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) of the Agricultural Research Council Plant Health and Protection division.

Figures 1–3. *Parapalystes lycosinus*. 1. Female from Kammanassie Nature Reserve, dorsal view. 2–3. Female from Namakwa District. Dorsal view (2) and ventral view (3). Credits: 1. Felix Riegel. 2–3. Cecile Roux.

Figures 4–7. *Parapalystes lycosinus*. 4–5. Anterior and dorsal views of carapace. 4. Showing the white band between the anterior and posterior eye row. 5. Showing the white line present from the middle posterior eye row to the white patch immediately anterior to the fovea. 6. Eye pattern. 7. Male palp. Credits: 4–5. Cecile Roux. 6–7. After Jäger & Kunz (2005).

TAXONOMY

Palystes lycosinus Pocock, 1900

Parapalystes lycosinus Pocock, 1900: 330; Croeser, 1996: 90 (designated male lectotype and female and subadult paralectotypes); Jäger & Kunz, 2005: 168; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010: 927; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2022: 61; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2024: 234.

Diagnosis: Total length 21 mm. Carapace as wide as long posteriorly evenly rounded (Figs 1 & 14); cephalic region posterior of eyes with a slight dome (Fig. 5). Carapace dark cover with a layer of setae that vary in colour from grey, fawn to white giving the carapace a mottled appearance (Fig. 5); a band of white setae present between the anterior and posterior eye rows (Fig. 4); a narrow white band originating between the posterior median eyes extend posteriorly to the fovea where it broaden and is surrounded on both sides by two dark triangular patches (Fig. 5); dark striae present originating from the fovea (Fig. 1); chelicerae are brownish-gray with a slightly darker terminal segment (Fig. 4); white band on clypeus absent with band fawn setae; sternum black (Fig. 3). The coxae are brownish gray dorsally and pale ochre-yellow on the underside, with brown tiger-like spot (Fig. 3). Legs dorsally same colour as carapace with mottled appearance; femora ventrally dark decorated with numerous small pale spots (Fig. 4); tibiae ventrally with dark and white bands (Fig. 3). Metatarsus and tarsus with dense scopulae (Fig. 15). Abdomen long oval; dorsum covered by setae layer with colour varying from fawn, grey to brownish; mid-line decorated with 3-5 paired triangular patches arranged in longitudinal line. Ventrally fawn to reddish brown with dark spots; two dark patches varying in shape and size are present below the epigynal groove and in front of the spinnerets (Figs 3, 11–13). Tibia of male palp armed at its distal end above with a single, slightly sinuous, basally stout, apically pointed spur directed forwards and outwards over the base of the tarsus (Fig. 7).

LIFESTYLE

Parapalystes lycosinus is a free-living wandering ground spider sampled from the Fynbos, Nama Karoo and Succulent Karoo in the Eastern, Northern and Western Cape. They were sampled with pitfall traps and most of the records from iNaturalist show them on rocky areas. The female deposits the white egg sac on the ground under rocks, while she stays in proximity to provide protection.

CONSERVATION STATUS

The species has a wide distribution and are known from three provinces. It is protected in the Eastern Cape in the Addo National Park, Fort Fordyce Forest Reserve and Commando Drift Nature Reserve. In the Western Cape it is known from the Karoo National Park (Pettersvlei) and Aardvark Nature Reserve and Kammanassie Nature Reserve.

Figures 8–16. *Parapalystes lycosinus*. 8–10. Abdomens dorsal view showing the variation. 11–13. Abdomen ventral view. 14–16. Habitus showing the colour variations. Credits: 10 & 14. Cecile Roux, Peter Webb and Felix Riegel. 11.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

South Africa (Fig. 17)

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Figure 17. Distribution records of *Parapalystes lycosinus* in South Africa. Showing the SANSA distribution records of material housed in the National Collection of Arachnida and the locations of iNaturalist "Research Grade" observations of *Parapalystes lycosinus* from <https://www.inaturalist.org> exported on 24 September 2025.

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